

EATING HABITS AND THE RISK OF METABOLIC SYNDROME IN ADOLESCENTS LIVING IN KHORESM REGION

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To analyze the eating habits of adolescents living in the Khorezm region; To determine the relationship between eating habits and components of metabolic syndrome; To develop recommendations to prevent the risk of developing metabolic syndrome

Introduction

In recent years, metabolic syndrome and its components - overweight, abdominal obesity, hypertriglyceridemia, hypo- or hypercholesterolemia, hypertension, and insulin resistance - have become widespread among adolescents worldwide. In Uzbekistan, including the Khorezm region, unhealthy eating habits, consumption of fast food, sweet drinks, and low-nutrient foods are increasing among adolescents. This situation increases the risk of developing metabolic syndrome and increases the risk of cardiovascular, endocrine, and other chronic diseases. Therefore, studying eating habits and assessing the risk of metabolic syndrome among adolescents is relevant.

Objective: To analyze the eating habits of adolescents living in the Khorezm region; To determine the relationship between eating habits and components of metabolic syndrome; To develop recommendations to prevent the risk of developing metabolic syndrome.

Methodology

The study was conducted using descriptive and analytical methods. Target group: 200 adolescents aged 12–18 years were selected from schools in the Khorezm region. Data were collected using questionnaires, 24-hour food diaries, and anthropometric measurements. Glucose, cholesterol, and triglycerides were measured through blood tests. The presence of metabolic syndrome was assessed according to IDF (International Diabetes Federation) criteria.

Results and discussion

ABSTRACT

In recent years, metabolic syndrome and its components - overweight, abdominal obesity, hypertriglyceridemia, hypo- or hypercholesterolemia, hypertension, and insulin resistance - have become widespread among adolescents worldwide. In Uzbekistan, including the Khorezm region, unhealthy eating habits, consumption of fast food, sweet drinks, and low-nutrient foods are increasing among adolescents. This situation increases the risk of developing metabolic syndrome and increases the risk of cardiovascular, endocrine, and other chronic diseases. Therefore, studying eating habits and assessing the risk of metabolic syndrome among adolescents is relevant.

According to the results of the study, 55% of adolescents consume fast food and sugary drinks at least 3 times a week. Only 28% of adolescents consume enough fruits and vegetables in their daily diet. Based on measurements: 22% of adolescents are overweight, 14% are characterized by abdominal obesity. Blood tests showed: 18% of adolescents had hypertriglyceridemia, 12% had hypercholesterolemia, and 9% had hypertension. A negative relationship was found between eating habits and components of metabolic syndrome: high consumption of fast food, sugary drinks, and lack of fruits and vegetables increases the risk of metabolic syndrome.

Conclusion

The dietary habits of adolescents in the Khorezm region increase the risk of developing metabolic syndrome. Excessive consumption of fast food, sugary drinks, and insufficient fruit and vegetable intake are the main risk factors. Preventive and educational interventions on healthy eating are important in reducing the risk of metabolic syndrome.

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